

ALUMINIUM CHLORIDE, A NEW REAGENT FOR THE CONDENSATION OF β -KETONIC ESTERS WITH PHENOLS. THE CONDENSATION OF RESACYL AND GALLACYLPHENONES CONTAINING LONG-CHAIN ACYL GROUPS

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4-Acylresorcinols containing long-chain acyl groups have been condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, giving the corresponding 5-hydroxy-6-acylcoumarin derivatives in all cases.

In a previous paper (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1942, 11, iii, 112) the authors showed that 4-stearyl-resorcinol condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of aluminium chloride giving 5-hydroxy-6-stearyl-4-methylcoumarin. This reaction has now been extended to other 4-acyl-resorcinols containing long-chain acyl groups. In this paper the similar condensation of 4-isovaleryl-, 4-palmityl-, and 4-lauryl-resorcinols has been described.

All the above ketones condense with ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of aluminium chloride in dry nitrobenzene solution in a manner similar to 4-stearylresorcinol, giving the corresponding 5-hydroxy-6-acyl-4-methylcoumarins (I, $R = C_4H_9$, $C_{15}H_{31}$, $C_{11}H_{23}$ respectively).

It is interesting to note that all the ketones condense smoothly at 100-110°; if the condensation is effected at higher temperature as done in the previous work (Sethna, Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228, 1066, 1424 *et seq*) there is a considerable diminution in the yield and the product is difficult to purify.

The constitution (I) assigned to the above coumarins follows from the fact that they show exactly similar reactions like 5-hydroxy-6-acylcoumarins described before (*loc. cit.*). They dissolve in alkali with non-fluorescent yellow colour and give colour test with alcoholic ferric chloride, and on Kostanecki acetylation, give chromono- α -pyrones (II). It may be mentioned here that 5-hydroxy-6-isovalerylcoumarin does not undergo the Kostanecki acetylation. The search of literature does not show any instance of an *iso*-ketone undergoing this reaction.

The above condensation could not be effected with sulphuric acid as condensing agent. 4-Palmityl- and 4-lauryl-pyrogallols do not condense inspite of various attempts

The above results are in harmony with those already obtained previously (*loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of 4-isovalerylcoumarin with Acetocetic Ester in presence of Aluminium Chloride: Formation of 5-Hydroxy-6-isovaleryl-4-methylcoumarin (I, $R = C_4H_9$).—4-iso-

Valerylresorcinol, used in this work, was prepared by Nencki's reaction. Resorcinol (3 g., 1 mol.) and ethyl acetoacetate (2.5 g., 1 mol.) were dissolved in dry nitrobenzene (5 c.c.) and added to a solution of anhydrous aluminium chloride (5 g., 2 mols.) in dry nitrobenzene (25 c.c.), the solution being protected from moisture by calcium chloride guard-tube. Copious hydrochloric acid fumes were evolved. The mixture was then heated in an oil-bath at 100-110° for about 1 hour with occasional shaking. When the evolution of acid fumes was negligible, the mixture was cooled, treated with ice and concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) and nitrobenzene distilled in steam. A brown oil remained which on treating with little alcohol gave a yellowish powder. This was collected and crystallised from boiling alcohol yielding fine, long, woolly needles, m.p. 127°; yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 70.0; H, 6.4. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.1 per cent).

The coumarin is sparingly soluble in boiling alcohol and hot acetic acid, and easily soluble in non-hydroxylic solvents. It gives red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and dissolves in alcoholic alkali with deep yellow colour without fluorescence.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by acetic anhydride-pyridine method (refluxing for 6 hours on a water-bath), crystallised from alcohol as needles, m.p. 121°. (Found: C, 68.3; H, 6.4. $C_{17}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 67.5; H, 6.0 per cent).

The *oxime* crystallised from acetic acid as small needles, m.p. 223°. The *semicarbazone* separated as needles from alcohol, m.p. 208°.

Clemmensen Reduction of 5-Hydroxy-6-isovaleryl-4-methylcoumarin: Formation of 5-Hydroxy-6-isoamyl-4-methylcoumarin.—The keto-coumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol and zinc amalgam (20 g.) added. Dilute hydrochloric acid (25 c.c. 1:1) was poured in and the mixture heated on a sand-bath. As the reaction proceeded, the coumarin dissolved. After heating for 4 hours a clear solution was obtained; it was filtered off from the unchanged amalgam, which was washed with acetic acid and the washings added to the main filtrate. On cooling, a colourless solid separated. It was collected and crystallised from acetic acid as small needles, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 73.7; H, 7.8. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 73.2; H, 7.3 per cent). The coumarin gives no colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. It is insoluble in aqueous alkali but turns deep yellow and dissolves in alcoholic alkali with deep yellow colour.

Condensation of 4-Palmitylresorcinol: Formation of 5-Hydroxy-6-palmityl-4-methylcoumarin (I, R = $C_{15}H_{31}$).—Dry 4-palmitylresorcinol (2 g.) and the ester (1 g.) were added to aluminium chloride (2 g.) dissolved in dry nitrobenzene (10 c.c.) and the mixture, protected from moisture by $CaCl_2$ guard-tube, was heated as before and then worked up similarly. The solid was crystallised from acetic acid and then from boiling alcohol as silky needles, m.p. 118°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 9.4. $C_{26}H_{38}O_4$ requires C, 75.4; H, 9.2 per cent).

The coumarin is sparingly soluble in hot alcohol and acetic acid and easily so in acetone and chloroform. It is insoluble in aqueous alkali but turns deep yellow and gives red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The above condensation could not be effected with sulphuric acid as a condensing agent.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared as before, crystallised from alcohol as small granules, m.p. 76°. (Found: C, 73.8; H, 8.6. $C_{28}H_{40}O_5$ requires C, 73.7; H, 8.8 per cent). The *oxime* and *semicarbazone* could not be prepared owing to the low solubility of the coumarin in alcohol.

Kostanecki Acetylation: Formation of 4:2'-Dimethyl-3'-tetradecylchromono-7':8':6:5- α -pyrone (II, $R_1 = C_{14}H_{29}$).—The coumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and fused sodium acetate (1 g.) were refluxed on an oil-bath at 150-160° for about 11 hours. The

mixture was then cooled and treated with cold water. The solid obtained was crystallised from boiling alcohol as needles, m.p. 133°. (Found: C, 76.3; H, 8.9; $C_{28}H_{46}O_4$ requires C, 76.7; H, 8.7 per cent). The chromono- α -pyrone is insoluble in alkali and gives no colour with ferric chloride.

Clemmensen Reduction: Formation of 5-Hydroxy-6-hexadecyl-4-methylcoumarin.—The coumarin was dissolved in hot alcohol and zinc amalgam (15 g.) added and after the addition of hydrochloric acid was heated on a sand-bath for 4 hours with occasional shaking; the solution was filtered off and on cooling gave a white solid which was collected and crystallised from dilute acetic acid as needles, m.p. 102°. (Found: C, 77.7; H, 10.1. $C_{28}H_{46}O_4$ requires C, 78.0; H, 10.0 per cent). The product turns deep yellow in alkali and gives no colour with ferric chloride.

Condensation of 4-Laurylresorcinol: Formation of 5-Hydroxy-6-lauryl-4-methylcoumrrin (I, $R=C_{11}H_{23}$). The resorcinol (6 g.) and the ester (3 g.) were added to aluminium chloride (7 g.) in dry nitrobenzene (30. c.c.) and treated as before. The product, obtained as before, crystallised from acetic acid and then from alcohol as fine needles, m.p. 116-17°, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 73.6; H, 8.5. $C_{22}H_{30}O_4$ requires C, 73.7; H, 8.4 per cent). The coumarin gives yellow colour in alkaline solution and deep red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The acetyl derivative, prepared as before, crystallised from alcohol as clusters of needles, m.p. 98°. (Found: C, 71.9; H, 8.1. $C_{24}H_{32}O_5$ requires C, 72.0; H, 8.0 per cent).

Kostanecki Acetylation: Formation of 4:2'-Dimethyl-3'-decylchromono-7':8':6:5- α -pyrone (II, $R_1=C_{10}H_{21}$).—The laurylcoumarin (1 g.), acetic anhydride and sodium acetate were refluxed as in the previous case and the product obtained similarly. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 154°. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 8.0. $C_{24}H_{30}O_4$ requires C, 75.4; H, 8.0 per cent). It gives no colour with ferric chloride and is insoluble in alkali.

Clemmensen Reduction: Formation of 5-Hydroxy-6-dodecyl-4-methylcoumarin.—The coumarin (1 g.) was reduced by zinc amalgam as before. On cooling, the reduction product separated, which was crystallised from dilute acetic acid as needles, m.p. 104°. (Found: C, 76.8; H, 9.2. $C_{22}H_{32}O_5$ requires C, 76.7; H, 9.3 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali but turns deep yellow and gives no ferric chloride colour.

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